

The Impact of Effective Communication on Organizational Performance a Case Study of Deaf Reach School Sukkur

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Abstract:

The current research investigates the impact of effective communication on organizational performance a case study of Deaf reach school sukkur. In this research study it is pointed out that applying random sampling technique only used for gathering data. Among the targeted area questionnaire were distributed by keeping the size of targeted probably 50 for collecting data and adding into research. Questionnaire is aligned in the pattern of 5-point Likert scale wise, like SA(strongly agree to SD(strongly disagree) will be applied to gather further data concerned with research from the working employees which are performing their duties in different department of NGOs. Questionnaire were pervading in two ways. Initial portion was connected with the demographic information of respondent and another part is concerned with data regarding too emotional intelligence in learning and decision making, then the data collected will be analyzed and sent through SPSS 24 Statistical software. The results indicate that enhance the performance of staff in terms of their relationship with the various Heads of Departments, Deans of Faculties, Students and University Community as a whole. This is evident in the most of the staff both academic and non-academic staff compel with the innovations, rules, and goals lead down. The move of the University to new technology of visibility and quality assurance most of the staff have keyed in into the process of activating their email address while uploading their CVs. However, the inability to meet up with the change has put a stumbling block in their path to success. Furthermore, it is quite evident that awareness of these innovations has exposed the faculty to new ways of doing things.

Keywords: Effective Communication, Organizational

1. INTRODUCTION:

All human interactions are form of communication. In this business world, nothing can be achieved without effectively communicating with employers, employees, clients, suppliers and customers. If you look most successful people in the world who have mastered the art of communication. Communication is the central to the success of human beings and organizations.

Business all over the world today is very challenging. To stay profitable at highly challenging and competitive global market economy all factors at production (men, machines and materials) should be wisely managed. Among the factors of production, human resource constitutes the biggest challenge because unlike inputs, employee management demands skillful handling of thoughts feeling and emotions to secure highest productivity. Effective organizational communication plays an important role in this challenge.(Akintaro & Shonubi, 2016)

Family Educational Service Foundation (FESF) is a non-profitable educational organization active in Pakistan since 1984. Family Educational Service Foundation is dedicated to enhancing the quality of life for all members of the community, especially those who are disadvantaged. This organization invests in educational development and provides innovative training programs and services to enable recipients to gain competency and self-sufficiency, empowering them to reach their full potential. Deaf Reach gave a very well received presentation to international deaf leaders and educators at this year's 17th World Deaf Congress held from July 28 to August 1st , 2015 in Istanbul, Turkey and attended by representatives from over 130 Countries.(Family Educational Services Foundation)

In today's world, sometimes called the "communication era", educational organizations are set up to integrate people into the new communicative, world. Effective communication in the school setting allows change and the proper shaping of the world, as well as providing a great advantage for the organization for reaching its objective.

In view of this understanding the effective communication will improve employee performance and also contribute to their retention is serious issue as employee turnover will be high as there high demand for services. Effective communication is best tools that can be used to attract in order to achieve organizational objectives. In this scenario this research examined the impact of effective communication on organizational performance as case study of Deaf Reach School Sukkur (Sindh) Pakistan.

2. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES:

The main purpose of the study was to identify the impact of effective communication on organizational performance.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Business communication also called organizational communication, plays an important role in the success of a company. The function of business communication include sharing information and motivating workers. Development, implementation and promotion of effective communication techniques with an organization involve understanding communication basics. Communication basics include the concept of channel (method of communication), encoding (the word choice you use in communicating your message) and decoding (how others interpret your message)(Internet).

Communication has been widely accepted by scholars and academies as the life hood of an organization because communication is needed for exchanging information, exchanging opinions, making plans and proposals, reaching agreement, executing decisions, sending and fulfilling orders and conducting sales (Alyssa-2006, Rotler-2006, & Blalock-2005).

According to Kotler, (2006), Communication is the means by which firms attempt to inform, persuade and remind consumers-directly or indirectly-about the products and brands that they sell. In a sense, communication represents the "voice" of the brands and is a means by which it can establish a dialogue and build relationships with consumers. Blalock (2005) posits that good communication matters because business organization are made up of people, and as Robert Kent, former dean of Harvard Business school puts it, "In business, communication is everything.

According to the World of Business Communication (Internet), every business aims to gain profit and in whatever type of business you may be, the bottom line is that you must earn something from it. No business person desires to make losses as this may lead to non-sustainability and eventual close down/liquidation.

According to Alyssa (2006), the ability to communicate, and communicate well is one of the biggest factors in business success. You could be an excellent designer, but if you are unable to promote your services and communicate effectively with clients and colleagues, your potential is limited. The principal areas where communication is essential include: pitching potential clients; clients meetings; consumer service; face-to-face networking; and marketing your business.

Effective communication is a process by which sender of message, received feedback from receiver in intended (Peter, 2016). Effective communication starts from the sender to its decoding by the receiver. It is said to be ineffective communication when receiver of the message did not decode the intended of the sender. It is through feedback that information achieves its desires results. Effective communication takes place when the person to whom it is intended, subsequently, the receiver understand the meaning intended and reacts accordingly (Berrels & A., 2010).

Effective communication is a transaction of ideas, directory command or guide into oral or written words, or actions on the path of the communicator in such a way that the receiver gets the same message and reacts in manner envisaged by the communicator (Victor & Akam, 2011). All aspects and points to effective communication in the organization, it gain in conclusion that channels of communication is one of the most effective way in a relationship and qualified managers have to pass over all stages of communication (Banihashemi, 2011).

Communication is a basic element in organizational structure and functioning. It is the key mechanism for achieving integration and coordination of the activities of specialized units at different levels in the organization.

Research spanning several decades has consistently ranked communication skills as crucial for managers. Managers spend 75 to 80 percent of their time in some form of written or oral communication. Although, often termed as 'soft' skill, communication in business organizations provide the critical link between core functions.

Communication here plays a very important role in the process of directing and controlling the people in the organization. Communication is essential for the success and growth of an organization. Therefore, communication gaps should not be allowed to occur in any organization. Effective business communication help in building the goodwill of an organization. Hence, it is necessary that you think before you communicate, be an active listener, be focused on your audience; and in your response, be brief and be gone (Management Study Guide, 1998-2001).

Business communication involves constant flow of information. Feedback is integral part of business communication. Organizations these days are very large and they involve a large number of people. There are various levels of hierarchy in an organization. The greater the number of levels, the more difficult is the job of managing the organization. There should be effective communication between superiors and subordinates in the organization, between organizations and the society at large, between management and trade unions, etc (Management Study Guide, 1998-2001).

According to Kibe (2014) investigated the effects of communication strategies on organizational performance. A descriptive research design was used in this study. 132 questionnaires were distributed employees. The finding of this research showed the importance of both the theoretical level and practical level. It concluded that for any organizational performance to be effective, an open communication environment should be encouraged. Once members of the organization feel free to share feedback, ideas and even criticisms at every level it increases performance.

Effective communication in the workplace is important for good organizational performance. Managers with good communication skills that they convey their ideas clearly so that subordinates understand what is required from them and can positively contribute to the organization. In contrast, a lack of communication can lead to employee frustration, lower productivity, absenteeism and increase employee turnover rate (Internet).

There are various forms of communication within an organization will use the kind of communication that suits them best. Whichever type of communication used is not an issue so long as the information gets to the right recipient and at the correct time (Kondrat, 2001).

1) Information Communication Technology (ICT)

There is a framework and several theories applied to the study of information communication technology of effective communication in organization, the theoretical framework within which study is situated are the innovation of theory.

The level of technology within the organization is another factor effecting the communication system in the organization. In that, organizations that have a higher level of technology have better efficiency of communications in terms of speed and accuracy (Hargie, 2000).

Technology can be used to enable or to oppress people at work (Coovert & Thompson, 2014). Attention is increasingly being devoted to the importance of technology and innovation at the macroeconomic level. This ranges from presidential encouragement (Reagan, 1985). The suggestion being made is not that technology should replace any existing tool but that a critical link between technology and strategy exists' (Kantrow, 1980) and that the attempt should be made to view technology in strategic terms. Different perspective have

been brought to bear on the strategy-technology relationship but all share the belief that technology can play a role in enhancing a firm's performance.

Technology has positive effects on business operations. No matter the size of your enterprise, technology has both tangible and intangible benefits that will help you make money and produce the results your customers demand. Technological infrastructure effects the culture, efficiency and relationships of a business. It also effect the security of confidential information and trade advantage(Internet).

Technology effects a firm's ability to communicate with customers. In today's busy business environment, it is necessary for employees to interact with clients quickly and clearly(Internet).

Communication technology, like email and teleconferences, makes organizational communication easily accessible. Using these methods of electronic communication can help make distance a non-factor in organizational communication. Communication technology lets your manager better collect data around the workplace, allowing her to make more inform decisions, such as how much of a raise you deserve. Technology also creates a more connected workplace. Today's technological advances have moved communications into a new realm, where messages are delivered almost instantly, tasks are assigned and managed by computer programs and people are even removed from the communication equation. And while most advances have improved workflow and efficiency, some concerns about the quality of business relationships have surfaced.

Hinds and Kiesler(1995, p.373) state that "many large organizations have installed a complex network of computer based technologies such as the telephone, facsimile, printing, voice mail, email and even videoconferencing technologies. These technologies increase the potential for communication within the organization. They also support the changing dimensions of communication.

Hinds and Kiesler(1995, p.374) also opine that "employees who need to collaborate and share information will use communication technology to communicate across organizational boundaries". "Communication technologies can be ranked by how well they suit collaboration, particularly they intense exchange of information required for planning and technical exchange" (Kraut-1990, Egado-1990, & Galegher-1990).

The effectiveness of any organization's communication systems forms an essential part of its working. Effective communication channels like instant messaging and conference calls over internet contribute highly to work productivity. As a result, the virtual office technology has removed workplace boundaries and has led to business expansion faster than we thought.

Effortless communication is the core of organizational efficiency. Since there are multiple layers of communication involved in businesses, including communication with clients, co-workers, peers, customers, and other stakeholders, the choice of communication channel can help make quick business decisions. The integration of technology has not only changed the pace at which inter and intra organizational communication works, but has also impacted the way work is done. It brings flexibility and ease of connectivity, which makes the global workplace mobile. The introduction of liquid computing is increasing efficiency by eliminating constraints like time, place and manner.

The Impact of Technology in Organizational Communication The relationship between technology and communication in today's organizations is significant. Technology can even change the way organizations are structured when a new system is introduced.

Hypothesis:

H2: There is a significant relationship between The impact of effective communication & employee performance of organizational performance and organizational performance.

H3: There is a positive impact of job stress, motivation and communication on effective communication and employee performance on organizational performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Impact of Effective Communication & Employee Performance On Organizational Performance: Organizational performance is a sign of the capacity of a company to efficiently to achieve independent goals (Vankatraman & Ramanujam, 1986). One of the elements that is assessable is the employees' performance through the level of their productivity. Several researchers have been introducing various methods to evaluate organizational performance (Prajogo & wong, 2007). This includes the quality, quantity, knowledge or creativity of individual towards the accomplished works that are in accordance with the responsibility during a specified period-in other words the assessment systems must have some standard parameters that can be relied upon.

➤ **Job Stress:**

In his earlier literature, it is mentioned that job stress is produced who one cannot properly coordinate available resources and job demands with personal abilities (French, 1975). He describes that job stress is derived from a situation of job environment that poses threat to an individual. Some companies may demand achieving a certain level of work, while their employees may be unable to cope with the given tasks. It is said that the demand exceed the capacity of an individual which simultaneously fails to satisfy the top management. Moreover, job stress has been known universally as a social problem (Mizuno, 2006). This is in line with the studies that have been conducted on the effect of job stress in the terms of medical matters such as heart disease, gastroenteritis, sleep disorder and other accidents that will decrease the rate of job performance, and the increase rate of absence and job displacement (Mcvisor,2003 & Mitoma2008).

The potential of job stress could arise from three aspects such as environment, organizational and individual (employee) factors. The possibility of stress affecting one's performance is great (Tuten & Neidermeyer, 2004). Each individual is exposed to a range of stressors both at work and in his or her personal life which ultimately affects work performance (Feddock, 2007).

➤ **Motivation:**

The employee motivation is obviously important. In fact, it is one of the most important and essential factors for the achievement of employees, and ultimately the organizational targets and goals (Berman et al., 2010). Ololube (2006) asserts that motivation to work, whether intrinsic or extrinsic are very essential in the lives of workers because they form the fundamental reason for working in life. It represents the complex forces and needs which provide the energy for an individual to perform a particular task (Shulze & Steyn, 2003). Moreover, employee motivation serves as an essential component of business operations whereby high motivation coincides with job satisfaction, a sense of pride in one's work, a lifelong commitment to organization which enhances performance and productivity (Linz et al., 2006).

➤ **Communication:**

With effective communication, a company is able to have good coordination among the teams or units in an organization whereby the absence of it will reflect problems in running business operations or critically cause the damage between individuals. It has been suggested that the persons who are involved in communication processes need to possess both basic skills and abilities, otherwise, the information could be missed to understand appropriately, and furthermore it depends on the facilities available in organizations and the actions of managers to see the acceptability of information in order to have an accurate deliverance. Furthermore, as one of the crucial elements, the managers have been asked to learn the feedback gained from the employees which probably affects their work motivation. This relates to the circumstances that are currently faced by the employees including the right time of delivering such information, thus, they may perform based on the messages they receive. In obtaining such a good performance, the managers must show the initiatives of developing and providing opportunities to learn new skills to their employees through the communication process.

Data Collection:

The data used for the study were obtained from both primary and secondary Data sources. The primary sources include direct information collected through administration of questionnaires in order to gain insight

into the research topic. The secondary data sources include journals, textbooks and other related publications both online and offline. Data were gathered through administering of questionnaires to employees of Deaf Reach School. In this research study it is pointed out that applying random sampling technique only used for gathering data. among the targeted area questionnaire were distributed by keeping the size of targeted probably 50 for collecting data and adding into research.

Questionnaire is aligned in the pattern of 5-point Likert scale wise, like SA(strongly agree to SD(strongly disagree) will be applied to gather further data concerned with research from the working employees which are performing their duties in different department of NGOs. Questionnaire were pervading in two ways. Initial portion was connected with the demographic information of respondent and another part is concerned with data regarding too emotional intelligence in learning and decision making, Then the data collected will be analyzed and sent through SPSS 23 Statistical software

Implications of effective communication on organizational performance Husain (2013) identified that the role played by communication during change in the business organizations as essential for successful change management. The employees are the key sources to bring about change in organizations. To encourage employees for desired change, organizations must address the apprehensions and issues related with them. Job insecurity should be decreased and a sense of community should be created so that employees may feel their responsibilities. The need for change and its advantages will motivate the staff to participate in change plan and execute it.

According to Kibe (2014) investigated the effects of communication strategies on organizational performance. A descriptive research design was used in this study. 132 questionnaires were distributed employees. The findings of this research showed the importance of both the theoretical level and practical level. It concluded that for any organizational performance to be effective, an open communication environment should be encouraged. Once members of the organization feel free to share feedback, ideas and even criticism at every level it increases performance.

Results

The Communication Process

The communication process consists of seven steps (Shannon & Weaver, 1949): message, encoding, transmitting, receiving, decoding, understanding and feedback. Communication is not an easy task, but attempt have been made to simplify it through illustration below:

Figure I a Communication Process Model:

Sex	SA	A	N	D	SD	Total
Male	50	8	4	7	5	74
Female	14	12	10	5	6	47
	64	20	14	12	11	121

Source: Field survey 2021

Cells	Fo	Ft	Fo-Ft	(fo-ft) ²	(fo-ft) ² ft
E ₁	50	39.14	10.86	17.94	3.0133
E ₂	8	12.23	-4.23	17.89	1.4628
E ₃	4	6.56	-4.56	20.79	2.4287
E ₄	7	7.34	-0.34	0.12	0.0163
E ₅	5	6.73	-1.73	2.99	0.4443
E ₆	14	24.86	-10.86	117.94	4.7442
E ₇	12	7.77	4.23	17.89	2.3024

Sex	SA	A	N	D	SD	Total
Male	40	15	9	4	1	69
Female	27	11	8	4	2	52
	67	26	17	8	3	121

Source: Field survey 2021

Cells	Fo	Ft	Fo-Ft	(Fo-Ft) ²	(Fo-Ft) ² Ft
E ₁	40	38.20	1.8	3.24	0.0848
E ₂	15	14.82	0.18	0.03	0.0020
E ₃	9	9.69	-0.69	0.47	0.0485
E ₄	4	4.56	-0.56	0.31	0.0679
E ₅	1	1.71	-0.71	0.50	0.2923
E ₆	27	22.14	4.86	23.61	1.0663
E ₇	11	8.59	2.41	5.80	0.6752
E ₈	8	5.61	2.39	5.71	1.0178
E ₉	4	2.64	1.36	1.84	0.6969
E ₁₀	2	0.99	1.01	1.02	1.0303
CALCULATED CHI-SQUARE					4.982

Source: Field survey 2021

To determine the tabulated chi-square value:-

Degree of freedom, = (R-1) (C-1) (2-1) (5-1) (at 5% significance) 1×4= 4 under 0.05

Conclusion and Recommendations

Likewise it was observed that communication techniques has enhance the performance of staff in terms of their relationship with the various Heads of Departments, Deans of Faculties, Students and University Community as a whole. This is evident in the most of the staff both academic and non-academic staff compel with the innovations, rules, and goals lead down. The move of the University to new technology of visibility and quality assurance most of the staff have keyed in into the process of activating their email address while uploading their CVs. However, the inability to meet up with the change has put a stumbling block in their path to success. Furthermore, it is quite evident that awareness of these innovations has exposed the faculty to new ways of doing things. ”

Conclusion

The finding of this research has shown that effective communication should be highly recommended to every organization in all the sectors of the economy. Any management both government establishment and private that is desirous of ensuring the success and efficiency of its workforce, should be conscious of

implementing effective communication programmed to their employees for better performances. Therefore, effective communication process should be an integral part of management strategy because it goes a long way to enhancing the realization of organizational goals. Hence not theoretical, but practical participation of staff in matters that, affect their creativity and performance. The objectives of effective communication programmes should be clearly stated so that all employee or workforce will be informed. Adequate communication techniques are advisable since it create easy understanding and cooperation in an organization. The study also established that effective communication enhances performances since employees performed better when there are informed or communicated to than those who are not informed. However inability of train the staff on the new innovations and techniques has made the lecturers insecure and overzealous in carrying out their duties. Thus, organization must spend time to determine the communication needs and finance the cost of it to get employees informed and be able to evaluate the impact of it on organizational activities.

Conclusively, effective communication to the management and staff is the panacea for sustained and increased productivity of the workforce and organizational performances. It is not enough to have a good ideal but awareness and participation of staff will go a long way to enhance organizational performance.

Recommendations

The effectiveness of communication is determined by both parties; hence it becomes necessary that they must pursue the same objective, which is high performance rate in all affairs of the institution. All cadres of staff should be involved in decisions and issues that affect their performance, for it will lead to organisational development and positive. Every organization endeavours to make effective communication an essential integral; part in effect management strategies to help minimize organizational conflict, less misunderstanding, improving information management and cordial relationship between management and workforce. Change is needed but when it is badly communicated it will likely lead to poor performance and negative outcome.

Consequently, all staff members should key into the google programme of the university to enable them be at abreast with the use of the google applications and email address. It should also be backed up with work's seminar to enlighten them on the important of effective communication, training and retraining to increase their performance in their academic and administrative responsibility. It also suggested that a result driven-communication since it gives room to measure results and performance as it the communication process within the organization and this in turn impacts on decision making, problem solving as some of the issues undergo a bureaucratic process and this slows down the dispute

Finally, an open communication environment is one in which all members of the organization feel free to share feedback, ideas and even criticism at every level, thereby encouraging staff to freely give their views without being victimized by the management. Therefore, follow up of information encouraged for organizational performance.

Appendix

“The impact of effective communication on organizational performance (Deaf Reach School Sukkur)

(Questionnaire)

The study is being conducted by researcher of MS/M.PHIL from MANAGAMENT SCIENCES SHAH ABDUL LATIF UNIVERSITY KHAIRPUR. The primary objective of this study is to find out how impact of human resource management practices on employees' performance. I wish to assure you that any response you make will be strictly confidential. If you have any query, you can contact at E-mail:

Section: (1)

1. Gender, 1. Male: () 2. Female: ()
2. Age: 1. 21-30 () 2. 31-40 () 3. 41-60 () 4. Above 61 ()
3. Qualification: 1. Intermediate () 2. Bachelor () 3. Masters () 4. M.Phil. ()

4. Income: 1. 10,000-25,000 () 2. 26,000-40,000 () 3. 41,000-60,000 () 4. Above 60,000 ()

Section: (2)

Please Tick (☐) your responses using the following scale:

(1= Strongly Disagree (SD), 2= Disagree (D), 3= Neutral (N) , 4= Agreed (A), 5= Strongly Agree) (SA)

S.NO	VARIABLES	RATING				
		S.D	D	N	A	S.A
01	management communicates employees' duties and control responsibilities in an effective manner					
02	communication channels are established for people to report suspected improprieties					
03	communication flow across the university adequately (e.g. from department to department) to enable people to discharge their responsibilities effectively					
04	management take timely and appropriate follow-up action on communications received from customers, vendors, regulators, or other external parties					
05	The university/School subject to monitoring and compliance requirements imposed by legislative and regulatory bodies					
06	This organization provides adequate information about policies and goals.					
07	This organization provides adequate information about important changes.					
08	Management is transparent					
09	People in the organization regularly share views on issues of importance.					
10	Departments in my organization communicate frequently with each other					
11	This organization always tells the truth.					
12	The organization's internal use of social media gives me a sense of belonging to the organization.					
13	Do you feel like you are able to speak honestly about issues that affect you in the workplace?					
14	How strong are you with the amount of control and involvement you have over the work you do					
15	The number of meetings I am expected to attend gets in the way of my ability to do my work					
16	I am confident about contributing to the organizational goals					
17	My superior shows interest in my personal growth and goals					
18	My superiors trust me with high responsibility assignments					

Thank you for your help in answering these questions

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